

DIVERSE WORKFORCE AND ITS IMPACT ON PERFORMANCE OF ORGANIZATION- A THEORETICAL APPROACH

Miss. Priya Saini

Research Scholar, Business Management,
Mewar University Chittorgarh Rajasthan

Dr. S.S.Chauhan

Research Supervisor,
Mewar University Chittorgarh Rajasthan
(India)

Abstract:

Workplace diversity is a must have for all organizations in a country who want to have social, economic and political gains. Diversity is generally said to mean acknowledging, understanding, accepting, valuing and celebrating differences among people with respect to age, class, ethnicity, gender, physical and mental ability, race, sexual orientation, spiritual orientation and public assistance status. By managing diversity, companies interact with different cultures and clients. It increases creativity, productivity, new attitudes, new language skills, global understanding, new processes, and new solutions to difficult problems.

It is because of this reasons that this literature was put together in a comprehensive way so as to let all the human resources, management, public and government leaders read and understand the importance of managing diversity at workplace.

Keywords: *Managing workplace diversity, organizational development, Performance.*

Introduction:

"Managers must understand different cultures and ask employees from various communities, what their views and beliefs are. Most workers will be willing to share experiences with managers who appreciate this diversity. Other employees might be suspicious and decide not to share anything with their supervisors. However, all of them will spread the word around that the manager is sensitive to ethnicity, boosting his or her reputation, and that of the organization," - Mugira.

The concept of diversity includes acceptance and respect. It means understanding that each individual is unique, and recognizing our individual differences. These can be along the dimensions of race, ethnicity, gender, sexual orientation, socioeconomic status, age, physical abilities, religious beliefs, political beliefs, or other ideologies. It is the exploration of these differences in a safe, positive, and fostering environment. It is about understanding each other and moving beyond simple tolerance to embracing and celebrating the rich dimensions of diversity contained within each individual. Diversity is a set of conscious practices that involve understanding and appreciating interdependence of humanity, cultures, and the natural environment; practicing mutual respect for qualities and experiences that are different from our own; understanding that diversity includes not only ways of being but also ways of knowing; recognizing that personal, cultural, and institutionalized discrimination creates and sustains privileges for some while creating and sustaining disadvantages for others; and building alliances across differences so that we can work together to eradicate all forms of discrimination. Workplace diversity refers to the variety of differences between people in an organization. That sounds simple, but diversity encompasses race, gender, ethnic group, age, personality, cognitive style, tenure, organizational function, education, background, and more. Diversity involves not only how people perceive themselves but also how they perceive others. Those perceptions affect their interactions for person-to-person basis. For this to be effective, one has to overcome language and stereotype barriers. Diversity management is a process intended to create and maintain a positive work environment where the similarities and differences of individuals are valued. The literature on diversity management has mostly emphasized on organization culture; its impact on diversity openness; human resource management practices; institutional environments and organizational contexts to diversity-related pressures, expectations, requirements, and incentives; perceived practices and organizational outcomes related to managing employee diversity; and several other issues.

Model of Gender Discrimination

Fig-01

What is diversity?

The world's increasing globalization requires more interaction among people from diverse cultures, beliefs and backgrounds than ever before. The society no longer works nor lives in an island; people are now part of the worldwide economy with competition coming from all over the continents. It is because of this reason that profit making, governments and non-profit making organizations need to embrace diversity so as to become more innovative and open to change. Embracing, maximizing and capitalizing on workplace diversity has become an important asset for management today.

After knowing that diversity is a very essential factor in any organization, every person should understand what it is. Diversity is generally said to mean acknowledging, understanding, accepting, valuing and celebrating differences among people with respect to age, class, ethnicity, gender, physical and mental ability, race, sexual orientation, spiritual orientation and public assistance status (Esty, Griffin and Schorr-Hirsh, 1995).

Diversity is increasingly recognized and utilized as an important organizational resource in regards to whether the goal is to be an employer of choice, to provide excellent customer service, or to maintain a competitive edge. Workplace diversity is a multi-faced concept that will continue to evolve as more industries move toward a global marketplace. It also has proven to have led to a perception of being fundamental for employee performance. This fundamental

belief forces managers to embrace and comprehend the concept of workplace diversity, its barriers and benefits.

The purpose of this research is to investigate the effect of work force diversify towards employee performance in an organization which focus into air line industry. The research also focuses on workforce diversity which includes the gender, age, ethnic and education background of the employees which is the most critical variables among all the others.

Benefits of Workforce Diversity

Diversity has multiple benefits to the workplace. One of the major principles of diversity says that a company that has diverse employees has a greater understanding of the global marketplace. According to DiversityWorking.com, employers reported that their diverse organizations benefit from a variety of viewpoints, higher productivity and profit due to company cultures that encourage employees to perform to their highest ability. Employers may also recognize immediate benefits of workplace diversity. Customers who speak different languages or come from overseas may require customer service in their language. In industries such as marketing and advertising, knowing what consumers across different backgrounds want is crucial to success. Advantages of having diverse workforce:

- 1) High level of Productivity: When management takes the welfare of its workers at heart by means of offering them proper compensation, health care and employee appraisal, It enables workers to feels that they belong to the company irrespective of their cultural background by remaining loyal and hardworking which helps to increase the company's productivity and profit.
- 2) Exchange of varieties of ideas and Team work: A single person taking on multiple tasks cannot perform at the same pace as a team could; therefore each team member brings to the table different ideas and offers a unique perspective during problem solving to effectively arrive at the best solution at the shortest possible time.
- 3) Learning and growth: Diversity at the workplace creates an opportunity for employee's personal growth. When workers are being exposed to new cultures, ideas and perspectives,it can help each person to intellectually reach out and have a clearer insight of their place in the global environment and hence their own surroundings
- 4) Effective Communication: Workplace diversity can immensely strengthen a company's relationship with some specific group of customers by making communication more effective. A

customer service personnel or representatives can be paired up with customers from their specific area or location, making the customer feel at home with the representative and thus with the company.

5) Diverse Experience: Employee and their co-workers that come from a diverse background bring to the table some amount of unique perceptions and experience during teamwork or group tasks. Pooling the diverse skills and knowledge of culturally distinct employees together can immensely benefit the company by strengthening the responsiveness and productivity of the team to adapt to the changing conditions.

Diversity in Relation to Culture and Performance

As the importance of diversity in the organizational context has increased manifold, most organizations would like to research on diversity–organizational culture linkage, its effect on diversity openness, and between diversity and performance both at individual and organizational levels. Patrick (2010) found that diversity determines not only the effects of the diversity within an organization but also the level of openness to dissimilarity characteristics among the organization’s members, work groups, and culture. Despite the technological wonders of today’s communication, international relations require us to deal with one another on a patterns of local interaction as the basis for coordination and collective action. The other principle focuses on the bridges across global divisions as the basis for information transfer and learning. Moreover, both principles capture important elements of what it takes for a task group to achieve success in reaching its goals. A team that does not develop the connections among their members, which enable it to coordinate effectively, faces an uphill battle. However, when such networks remain concentrated among homogeneous sets of individuals, the team fails to generate the learning that can only come from interaction among different individuals. The biggest driver for higher level diversity strategy is the need to tap the creative, cultural, and communicative skills of a variety of employees and to use those skills to improve company policies, products, and customer experiences. Advances in technology and the advent of a global economy bring the people of the world closer together than ever before. Given this fact, businesses, educational systems and other entities are investigating ways to better serve their constituents. This includes being able to attract and retain the best and most qualified workers. Organizations that can develop and employ the necessary policies and procedures to do this will maintain a competitive advantage

among their counterparts and increase their effectiveness. To achieve success and maintain a competitive advantage, we must be able to draw on the most important resource such as the skills of the workforce. With the increasing richness of diversity in the workforce, we need to expand our outlook and use creative strategies to be successful. Employees can provide this resource. This study identifies the effect of workforce diversity toward employees' performance in Malaysia's airline industries

Research objectives

The first aim of this research is to provide insights and in-depth understanding of the workforce diversity that will affect the employee performance in an organization.

- To find the most important strategies adopted to enhance workplace diversity.
- To identify most frequently encountered barriers for accepting workplace diversity.
- To find out ways to increase awareness about workplace diversity.
- Investigate the relationship of gender towards employee performance in an organization.
- Investigate the relationship of education background towards employee performance in an organization.

Based on the theoretical review we proposed a conceptual model that shows the factors mediating work force strategy & performance link

Fig-02

Literature Review

Workforce diversity refers to the ways that people differ that can affect a task or relationship within an organization such as age, gender, race, education, religion, and culture. It is the exploration of these differences in a safe, positive, and nurturing environment. It is about understanding each other and moving beyond simple tolerance to embracing and celebrating the rich dimensions of diversity contained within each individual within the organization (**Carrell, 2006**).

Key literature has been reviewed to provide a foundation for the research discussion. This literature is used to define the concepts that will be used and provide a foundation for consideration of how well the pragmatic literature on the subject defines the concepts at hand. The theoretical foundation of the research comes from the sociological concept of the social network, while key foundational texts include research on two different perspectives on social networks, the information and decision making perspective and the social diversity perspective.

In general, the term “work force diversity” in our context can be defined as similarities and differences among employees in terms of age, ethnicity, gender, and education background. However, when an employee decides to switch his or her working environment, they have to face “culture shock” at the work place. This is because the employee has to learn the new language and adapt to different cultural beliefs that has long embed within the people in the working environment. Therefore, in adapting Brown (2008) diversity in the workplace, this study seek to explore its variable impact of gender, age, ethnicity, and education background on employee performance in the airline industry which comes with diversified work force in a package.(**Mercy Gacheri Munjuri,2012**)

The study best practices for leaders include-

- Making diversity an organizational priority.
- Developing a strong knowledge base about the value of diversity within the Organization.
- Developing institutional allies beyond the library on the diversity agenda.
- Developing, focusing and sharing one’s vision of diversity, practicing that vision.
- Committing human and fiscal resources to the diversity agenda. (**William’s 1999**)

Workforce diversity refers to organizations that are becoming more heterogeneous with the mix of people in terms of gender, age, race, and education background **(Robbins, 2009)**.

Today's managers are responsible for both leading employees and responding to the needs of customers who are more ethnically and culturally diverse, older, and in greater need of child and elder care. Leaders in both the public and the private sectors are focusing more attention on the issue of diversity. Whether the goal is to be an employer of choice, to provide excellent customer service, or to maintain a competitive edge, diversity is increasingly recognized and utilized as an important organizational resource.**(Lee kah mun,2011)**

Diversity and blatant forms of discrimination has been one element of some generations in the United States and other countries throughout the world due to people's stereotypes and cultural differences. While stereotypes and biases still exist in these countries, the negative impact of most blatant discriminatory practices have certainly been reduced and professionals now seem to have a much fairer "playing field" in reaching the ranks of management than ever before.**(Bahaudin G. Mujtaba,2007)**

Most attention on diversity management focused on the organizational decision maker who is prejudiced against certain groups and who allows these prejudices to influence how he or she treats employee. Moreover, they become embodied in organizational policies and practices that systematically disadvantage some employees. As an extension, employee diversity does not necessarily boost creativity, market share, or competitive advantage. In fact, research suggests that left un-managed, employee diversity is more likely to damage morale, increase turnover, and cause significant communication problems and conflict within the organization.**(Loriann and Carol, 2007)**

Steps to follow in managing workplace diversity

Having now known that diversity in the workplace involve bringing people together who have different backgrounds, religions and age groups into a cohesive and productive unit; advances in communication technology, such as the Internet and cellular phones, have made the marketplace even a more global concept. In order to survive, a company needs to be able to manage and utilize its diverse workplace effectively. Managing diversity in the workplace should be a part of the culture of the entire organization. This process of managing diversity is an on-

going process that unleashes the various talents and capabilities which a diverse population bring to an organization, community or society, so as to create a wholesome, inclusive environment, that is “safe for differences,” enables people to “reject rejection,” celebrates diversity, and maximizes the full potential of all, in a cultural context where everyone benefits (Rosado, 2006). By managing diversity at the workplace, organizations create an inclusive and harmonious environment which enhances good reputation of the organization with people seeking jobs hence able to attract the best workers in the market. The employees feel valued, rewarded and motivated while working in an organization that manage diversity. According to a research done worldwide three million employees indicated that diversity brings about satisfaction and organizational performance. It was also found out that creating an inclusive and harmonious environment was a key driver in employee engagement and commitment. Managing diversity creates greater employee engagement which at the end leads to reduced labour turnover. The following are steps on how to manage diversity in a workplace :-

Step I – Develop a recruitment strategy that stresses on the need for diversification. As an organization, develop policies and guidelines for staff conduct and ensure that each staff member has a copy. Include the channels and

procedures for grievances and ensure confidentiality for everyone. Ensure that the rules and guidelines are fair and transparent and apply to all staff, including the management.

Step II - Train recruitment personnel. This will make them experts in diversification matters. Provide them with the skills to analyze the current workforce and fill skills gaps. Ensure that candidates are chosen solely because they are the best fits for the jobs, and for no other reason.

Step III - Model good behaviour and enforce cultural sensitivity management training and appropriate conflict management training for management staff. An effective training program will first have management staff analyze their own diverse backgrounds and how they may have shaped prejudices that could affect the work place.

Step IV - Invest in cultural sensitivity training for all staff to facilitate better communication and promote tolerance. A good training program is one that staffs consider a positive experience and one that avoids using an accusatory tone. Teams are more successful when all members appreciate the value in diverse skills, education and experience.

Step V - Seek periodic feedback from staff and management in the form of a questionnaire or staff survey. Analyze and communicate the results to staff, identifying any progress made in staff

satisfaction and highlight any diversity or conflict issues so that they can be addressed before they become unmanageable.

Step VI - Encourage open communication and teamwork across work functions. Horizontal communication is more relevant in business environments where social media networking platforms are causing hierarchical boundaries to disappear. Encourage employees to work together to solve problems and consider incentives and rewards for successful projects.

Step VII - Plan an annual event to break down formal barriers and improve staff morale. Retreats and informal gatherings can promote better interpersonal relationships and foster a culture of inclusiveness.

Conclusion

A diverse workforce is a response to a changing world and marketplace. It is a process intended to create and maintain a positive work environment where the similarities and differences of individuals are valued, so that all can reach their potential and maximize their contributions to an organization's strategic goals and objectives. Diverse work group brings high value, good reputation and high productivity to the organization. Respecting individual differences will benefit the workplace to enjoy a competitive edge and enhance motivation of employees. Diversity management benefits associates by creating a fair and safe environment where everyone has access to opportunities. Management tools in a diverse workforce should be used to educate everyone about diversity and its issues, including laws and regulations. Most workplaces are made up of diverse cultures, so organizations need to learn how to adapt to be successful. How organizations manage diversity from today forward will determine the long-term success or failure in the global marketplace.

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